

METHODS FOR ASSESSING STUDENTS' DEVELOPMENT IN EDUCATION

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Abstract. *The issue of evaluating students' development in education is examined through the lens of modern pedagogical approaches and teacher skills. This problem is explored in depth by pedagogical researchers, who propose solutions grounded in theoretical frameworks.*

Keywords: *theoretical frameworks, modern approaches, educative technology, diagnose, common method, capability, behavior, inseparableness.*

First of all, it is worth noting that it is difficult to achieve great heights in education without achieving success in upbringing. For this, it is necessary to understand the essence of the concept of "upbringing" of pupils. Unfortunately, no dictionary provides theoretically a scientific definition of this level directly as a problem. At the same time, in several pedagogical studies, it is emphasized that the social, biological and geographical environment surrounding a person, and the noblest personal characteristics manifested in his(her) interaction with people, determine the upbringing of the pupils. On the basis of determining "pupil's upbringings" in all educational institutions, unity and continuity are ensured in the educational process, and an opportunity is created to learn the level of formation of pupil's personal characteristics and qualities, which are implemented in the system of interpersonal relations. Currently, the problem of determining the education of pupils is recognized as one of the new directions of teacher's pedagogical skill and is a research stage that is theoretically developed by our pedagogic scientists. The definition of education has not been fully reflected in pedagogical scientific literature, which complicates its scientifically based implementation in educational technologies. At the same time, teachers and educators of various categories, such as parents, cannot always give a sufficiently objective assessment of its results. As a result, the education level of pupils of the same character is evaluated differently by wide range of teachers and educators. It is impossible to solve these shortcomings without relying on scientifically-theoretically developed conditions to ensure integrity and continuity in education and upbringing.

Determining whether the student has been upbringing, education (diagnostics) is a process that determines the level of formation of personal characteristics and qualities of the student, which is carried out by the teacher in the system of interpersonal relations. Based on the analysis of its results, it is possible to improve and enrich the main elements of unity and continuity in educational institutions, and identify and correct deficiencies on time.

The main features of the process of determining the level of "pupil's education" are determined as a result of the use of a system of special methods developed on the basis of the interrelationship of pedagogy and psychology, as well as other disciplines. Pedagogical scientists such as Ya.S.Turbovsky, N.V.Kuzmina, I.P.Rachenko, V.P.Simonov, A.V.Hristeva propose to study the determination of the level of "pupil's education" in three groups:

- wide spreaded method;
- traditional method;
- diagnostic method.

The use of dialectical principles, such as the transition from quantitative to qualitative changes, the unity and struggle of opposites, and the laws of negation, is prevalent in educational methods. These principles are applied to analyze all phenomena of objective reality, offering teachers precise insights into the subjects they study, while focusing on clarifying final results.

Traditional methods of evaluating education allow for more accurate results and are well-established among educators. One such method is observation, which involves assessing students' personal activities, natural talents, and educational characteristics by gathering and analyzing evidence related to their actions, behavior, and personal traits. This method provides insights into students' educational levels based on their observable activities.

Another commonly used method is diagnostic assessment, which involves individual diagnostic interviews. This method evaluates student's educational level by examining the coherence and continuity of their development, providing teachers with a deeper understanding of students' inner worlds, beliefs, and aspirations. It also helps address students' issues, encourage positive actions, and focus on improving any identified shortcomings.

Additionally, the analysis of activity results is used as a final training method. This involves assessing students' educational levels based on their performance in social and other activities outside of educational settings, ensuring coherence and continuity. This method considers students' actions, interests, achievements, and shortcomings to evaluate their career orientation, character, and overall development.

Other methods described in pedagogical and psychological literature include:

- Document Analysis: Reviewing documents related to student's personality, such as descriptions and reviews.
- Experimental Method: Observing educational traits in controlled conditions where specific qualities are expected to emerge.
- Questionnaire Method: Analyzing students' responses to questions posed by the teacher, either in written or oral form.
- Independent Characteristics Method: Evaluating and discussing external opinions about student's upbringing.
- Biographical Method: Reviewing person's past work and experiences from a socio-psychological perspective.

Enhancing the reliability of educational assessment results can be achieved through specialized methods, often used by professional psychologists in psychodiagnostics. These methods, prevalent in educational systems worldwide, involve analyzing responses to tailored questionnaires and developing individualized educational plans. Notable personal questionnaires by psychologists like G. Eysenck, R. Kettel, and J. Taylor, as well as local psychologists' adaptations, are widely utilized in this context.

In recent years, survey methodologies have been developed and put into practice with the help of computer technologies. It provides access to the inner world of pupils and expands the possibilities of its use not only by professional psychologists, but also by teachers of various categories. They can also be used in self-diagnosis (reflection). Based on the above-mentioned opinions, teachers and educators-coaches in the educational system of our country should pay attention to the following processes in order to ensure consistency and continuity in their pedagogical activities and achieve high results:

Education is a process of all-round development of a person, formation of his consciousness, behavior and worldview based on a certain, clear goal and socio-historical experience, and not to forget that it has been the basis for determining the content of social relations and organizing them in any system and time.

Education of the young generation is organized based on specific goals in different places and times. A number of tasks are solved in the process of establishing social education. Ensuring that the goals and tasks of education are determined based on the essence of the social system, the level of development, the content of social relations, as well as the worldview, aspirations, dreams and wishes of the citizens of the society.

3. Along with the knowledge of pedagogical skills, teachers in their professional activities should thoroughly acquire the knowledge of psychological diagnosis, education technology, that is, they should know the individual algorithm of their behavior, the forms of education, and be able to perfectly perform all the operations for the implementation of any education method.

In conclusion, the integration of dialectical principles into educational methods facilitates a comprehensive analysis of teaching and learning processes, allowing for precise insights and enhanced understanding. Traditional evaluation methods, such as observation and diagnostic assessment, provide valuable insights into students' educational levels and personal development by examining their activities, talents, and behavioral traits.

The analysis of activity results, alongside document reviews, experimental observations, and questionnaire assessments, further enriches the evaluation process by offering diverse perspectives on students' performance and growth. These methods collectively contribute to a more accurate and nuanced understanding of educational outcomes.

The use of specialized techniques from psychodiagnostics, including tailored questionnaires and individualized educational plans, underscores the importance of adapting assessment methods to meet the unique needs of each student. By incorporating these varied approaches, educators can achieve greater reliability and effectiveness in assessing and supporting student development. The emphasis on continuous improvement and adaptation of assessment strategies ensures that educational practices remain responsive to evolving educational challenges and opportunities.

REFERENCES

1. Раченко И.П. Диагностика развития педагогического творчества учителя. – Пятигорск, 1992. –196 с.
2. Крутецкий В.А., Балбасова Е.Г. Педагогические способности, их структура, диагностика, условия формирования и развития: Учебное пособие. – М.: Прометей, 1991.- 112 с.
3. Кузьмина Н.В. Педагогическое мастерство учителя как фактор развития способностей учащихся. //Вопросы психологии. 1984. №1. –С.16.
4. Симонов В.П. Диагностика личности и профессионального мастерства преподавателя. //Учебное пособие для студентов педвузов, учителей и слушателей ФПК. – М.: Межд. пед. академия, 1995. –189 с.